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Specialized on-line technologies as an incentive feature of foreign language learning

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Abstract. The article deals with the problem of motivation of technical students for studying foreign languages. We present on-line platform Coursera as a motivation technique of foreign language learning.

Key words: motivation, method, platform, foreign language learning.

Nowadays, the problem of motivation is actively studied abroad. It should be emphasized that the notion of motivation is studied under different angles of view. K.A. Noels, L.G. Pelletier, R. Clément and R.J. Vallerand work on the problem of motivational orientations and self-determination theory [3]. R.W. Roeser and S.C. Peck study the question of self, motivation, and self-regulated learning in contemplative perspective [4]. M. Vansteenkiste, J. Simons, W. Lens, K.M. Sheldon and E.L. Deci investigate the synergistic effects of intrinsic goal contents and autonomy-supportive contexts [5]. The relationship between classroom activities, motivation, and outcomes in a university language-learning environment is shown in the work of J. Bernard [1]. A review of language learning motivation theories is given in F. Keblavi’s article [2]. But the research of the distant courses as method of foreign language learning motivation for technicians is not yet carried out.

The purpose of our report is to comment on specialised distant courses as a method of foreign language learning stimulation for the students of technical departments.

People are commonly known to be forced to learn foreign languages from the times of the Tower of Babel building. In regard to Ukraine, students from our country learn a lot of languages in dependence on country they are going to visit. The most widespread are English, German, French, Polish, Spanish and Italian. Over the last years, increasing attention is paid to Chinese, Japanese, Arabic and Jewish. Mainly, Ukrainian students

learn foreign languages for the purpose of working or studying abroad. Such kind of study is relevant both for philologists and technicians. Students have countless occasions of possibilities to learn foreign languages. They can study languages in higher educational institutions and numerous courses. However, future technicians, who do not want to continue their career abroad, need more attentive attitude to their motivation.

It is widely accepted that every student must learn foreign language if he has it in program, nevertheless, it does not always work. There are plethora methods of improving language-learning in Ukraine. Every teacher has an opportunity to pass an appropriate kind of specialized courses. However, in our view, the method of motivation for studying is one of the most effective ones. Taking into consideration that ordinary technical students, who plans to stay in Ukraine, do not have enough motivation to study a foreign language; we came to assumption that they need any possible additional kind of motivation. According to the previous investigations, it can be a specialized technical course.

The most effective platform for our needs is Coursera which pools the resources of studying technical courses and language improvement. Every teacher has an opportunity to motivate the students with the help of studying more in their speciality. As it was previously mentioned, even the students without special needs in foreign practice want to improve their professional skills to be on labour-market in demand. Thus, we rely on the course in Physics, Math, Chemistry, or Computer Sciences can be an incentive factor for foreign language learning.

Consequently, we consider that methodologists and ordinary teachers of foreign languages should use Coursera and other educational platforms to intensify the effect of requisite perception of foreign language learning for technical students.

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